

Connotations in semiotic systems of visual art (through the example of works by M. A. Vrubel)

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Abstract

In art connotations spread denotative structures. Correspondingly, the role of connotations in visual artworks should be as important as it is in systems of verbal information. Hence, developed connotative structures are found in visual artwork. Connotations of visual artworks are based on fundamental codes and develop their basic text. Representamens of denotations and connotations are interrelated and organized in system-structural formations of signals. Text of a visual artwork directs the actualization of connotations on the basis of its principal meanings and communicative structure. Connotations form semantic fields corresponding to basic meanings and text of artworks. These connotations, hidden from direct perception, are discussed with respect to the works of Vrubel.

1. Connotations of visual art as objects of theoretical semiotics

Connotations belong to the central objects of semiotic studies. Connotation codes and signs are manifested widely in human verbal communication where they serve as basic meaning-forming units (Danesi 1999). Rich connotations appear each time we deal with a natural human communication (unlike the information of business messages). In art, which involves broad and indefinite spheres of knowledge and communication, connotations spread and subordinate denotative structures. In the studies of literature and poetry, linguosemiotic models and methods reveal in detail various connotations and connect them with the structure of art text (Lotman 1970). Correspondingly, the role of connotations in visual artworks should be as important as it is in the systems of verbal information. Hence, developed connotative structures are found in visual artworks; these are connotations that I have analyzed earlier (Somov 2005). In the picture *Boyaress Morozova* by V. I. Surikov, the hidden signs of the

two-finger cross sign, Virgin, trumpeting Angel, Strelets' poleaxes, animal faces, etc., can be read in the crowd and landscape elements. The examination of *Madonna of Petrograd* by K. Petrov-Vodkin reveals hidden representations of the awful face of the city, suspended bells, arched motives of ancient Russian architecture, the expression of the epoch of revolution, and the germination of new life via a new color structure of Madonna's clothes typical of traditional icon-painting.

The analysis of various objects of architecture and the artificial environment of visual artworks demonstrated an extreme importance of hidden connotative formations, which are related to culture and text in a complex way (Somov 1985b, 1990).

Denotations and connotations of visual artworks are actualized in the processes of visual perception *by codes* (Bignell 1997), *linguistic type, text* (including adjacent denotations and connotations), and *context*. This idea corresponds to a known model of structure of the communicative act (Jakobson 1960). Codes and languages implemented in this domain of communication represent all Semiotic Humanity Systems (Halliday 1987). The semiotics divide codes into natural and cultural ones (Chandler 1994). *Natural codes* form signs and actualize their meanings in the process of perception based on fundamental mechanisms of the production of sensory information. *Cultural codes* form signs and actualize their meanings based on interrelations generated in different areas of communication (Hall 1980; Fiske 1982). Linguistic types generate sign formations on the basis of stable units and rely upon linguistic languages and different texts of culture.

The connotations of artworks exist due to codes and languages and simultaneously rely upon text and context. *Text* of a visual artwork directs the actualization of connotations on the basis of its principal meanings and communicative structure. *Context* directs the actualization of connotations in different areas and binds them by more general systemities. I have tried to demonstrate this role of text and context in the formation of connotations in analyzing the aforementioned works (Somov 2005). Natural codes are most important for the formation of connotations in a visual channel of communication. They have been examined in neurophysiology and psychophysiology as mechanisms in the production of sensory information (Somjen 1972). Natural codes provide the relations between perceived perceptual characteristics and real objects, as well as the relations of perceived information elements with general organizing structures. This corresponds to the differentiation in the sign model of C. S. Peirce: (1) interpretants, (2) objects, and (3) representamens (Somov 2003). This also corresponds to Lemke's triad: (1) orientation, (2) representation, and (3) organization. In connection with this, it is

possible to speak about a certain independence of three information-producing submechanisms in the mechanisms of fundamental and other codes. In order to simplify the discussion, let us call these submechanisms (1) *intentional codes*, (2) *codes of objective character*, and (3) *organizing codes*. *Intentional codes* enhance the production of information related to fundamental human intentions and possess a pronounced emotional aspect (danger, anxiety, sexual appeal, pleasant and unpleasant objects, friendly and aggressive features of individuals, etc.). In cultural codes of the visual communicational channel, they turn into visual coding of emotions and feelings and fine tints of individual interrelations. *Codes of objective character* provide the production of information about objects (feeling of one's own movement and location, movement and location of surrounding objects, their dimensions, heaviness or lightness, hardness or mildness, and animation). In cultural codes of the visual communication channel, they appear as various systems of symbols of relations and structures of denoted objects and develop into the production and transmission of various referent meanings. *Organizing codes* contribute to the production of information about the structure of information itself (feelings of symmetries, rhythms, directions of signal changes, hierarchies of their meanings, etc.). In cultural codes of visual communication channel, they appear as systemities of signs of represented objects and their representaments, systemities of visual signals (direction, axes, lines, focus points, geometrical similarities, whole color configurations, etc.), and systemities of designates constructed by pictures. Distinguished code types can be interpreted as corresponding to the aspects of sign systems of Morris: pragmatics, semantics, and syntactics (Somov 2003). In connection with semiotical ideas, all codes of fundamental character are incarnated in stable systems (forms) relating plans of content and expression (Hjelmlev 1961; Chandler 1994). For fundamental codes of the visual communication channel, this is supported by semiotic studies of architecture (Broadbent 1977). In particular, it is possible to distinguish here: (1) the features of intentionality (Somov 1985a), (2) the features of objects' structure, their weight, dynamics, tectonics, size, heaviness, lightness, etc. (Somov 1986, 1990), and (3) features of subordination to a general organization of information (Somov 1985b, 1990).

The fundamental mechanisms in the production of sensory information, being implemented in visual perception, have various manifestations in visual art. (1) *The predominance of features of intentional codes* in images (contours and lines: mild and coated or hard and dynamic, closed or open, smoothed or angled) generates different intentions and corresponding emotions. Intentional codes condition different disperse and indefinite meanings of picture connotations (tension, sharpness, relaxation,

mildness, tenderness, aggression, etc.). (2) *The predominance of features of codes of objective character* promotes the interpretation of images as information about represented objects: their motion, location, mutual distances, forces, and inclinations, including the spectator's movement among these objects. A significant part of this information refers to denotations, but it is not less important for the formation of connotations. Depicted human silhouettes, objects of environment, and landscapes can contain movements of water or air, plant growth, states of light, earth tectonic structure, spatial structures, and energy rhythms. Codes of objective character are also directed towards the recognition of object classes; this is manifested as identification. Identification is incarnated in the formation of denotations. However, many connotations are based on identifications. This is most apparent in the recognition of self-like creatures (living things, animals, or humans). Anthropomorphic connotations are widespread in architectural forms, objects of environment, and visual artworks (Somov 1990). Allusions to a human silhouette or face in the contour of clouds, mountains, or trees promote the creation of the image and spirit of a picture. In particular, these allusions are extremely important in the visual artworks mentioned above. In *Boyaress Morozova*, hidden icons of a trumpeting Angel, Virgin, and animal snouts spread in the crowd form a range of important meanings of the picture; in general, they form a semantic hierarchy from celestial to terrestrial. In *Madonna of Petrograd*, the face with bared teeth assigns a special spirit to a represented historical situation. The importance of such connotations presumes the relation between semiotical theory and identification models. Models of this kind were developed in the process of perception creation. Their basic essence is the setting of a certain hyperplane in the space of characteristics. This hyperplane is initially set by classes of characteristics (Rosenfeld 1969: 129–132). Codes can be regarded as classes, while identifications can be regarded as procedures for setting hyperplanes in spaces of characteristics. An image should contain some groups of characteristics corresponding to the codes participating in identifications. The distinctness and concreteness of these identifications depend on quantitative representation, system interrelations, and spatial allocation of characteristics, which support identifications. (3) *The predominance of features of organizing codes* mainly promotes the interrelations among connotations inside a text. General directions of movement of active elements, repetition of configurations, or geometrical similarities of major icons relate elements with groups and form a sign community. *The interrelation of fundamental codes* of different types (1, 2, and 3) determines a general structure of visual artworks, i.e., the interrelations among different layers. Layers of visual artworks are formed like layers of any type of potential

information, like heterogeneities containing indispensable characteristics, differences/similarities, and units formed in these relations and according to these characteristics. This corresponds to the idea of difference/similarity interpreted as the basis of language (Saussure 1959), of difference interpreted as the basis of information (Ashby 1956), and of heterogeneity (diversity) interpreted as the objective basis of information (Ursul 1971). In the concrete semiotic analysis of visual artworks, differences, interrelations, and typical features of organization of different layers are quite apparent. The most successful example is, to my mind, the analysis conducted by Meyer Schapiro. Analyses of this kind clearly distinguish active characteristics, contrasts, and authentications forming a visual tissue of work that potentially carries definite meanings and various denotations and connotations. The models of stratification approach (Prieto 1964) and their recent variations (Eco 1976; Sharov 1999) promote the specification of level structure and interrelations of different levels of visual artworks. This makes it possible to delimit *basic levels* in visual artworks and corresponding system-structural formations: *semantic systems, signs, representamens, and signals* (Somov 2005). Semantic systems can be regarded along the directions from objects to interpretants. Correspondingly, each *connotation* can be regarded as a *system-structural formation including representamens, objects, and interpretants, and interrelated with the layer of picture signals* via representamens, as it is illustrated by aforementioned examples. In particular, objects of connotation are the Strelets' poleaxes of the seventeenth century lifted over the crowd; their representamens are crescent configurations and lines, while their interpretants are ferocious forces of state power promising to punish the apostates. The 'root system' of this connotation accretes with the general text systemity: interpretants correspond to the major historical meaning of the picture, objects correspond to the environment of the seventeenth century, and representamens correspond to the representaments of denotations and other connotations and system-structural formations of signals. General principles of information production explain why all these interrelations are important for the existence of connotations. Some authors have shown that the human nervous system tends to construct unambiguous, clear, credible, internally related and consistent, capacious, and compact models of the environment, suitable for forecasts (Turner and Poeppel 1988). Semiotics describes the explanatory models of this kind in a simpler and more precise way. The set of principles of information production corresponds in general to the semiotical explanatory principle of hesitation-faith of C. S. Peirce. Based on the substantiation of naturalistic essence of his semiotic theory (Liszka 1996), I have tried to substantiate the naturalistic character of this principle and its different manifestations

in information production. The analysis demonstrates that the effect of this principle in different layers of sign systems can be regarded as structural organization. In particular, *structural organization along the line of intentional codes* generates the unified expression of pictures. *Structural organization along the line of codes of objective character* promotes the reflection of structures of real objects and their identification, i.e., forms convincing graphics. *Structural organization along the line of organization codes* generates the interrelations of relations and elements of a picture at each construction level: signs, sems, representamens, and signals. Developed means and techniques of this kind are apparent in the layers of representamens and signals where a convincing visual organization is formed, evolving into a so-called ‘decorativeness’ (Somov 1975).

Single connotations of visual artworks tend to be subordinated to structural organization of different levels and systems. Evolving at the levels of signs proper, they are conditioned, first of all, by semantic systems of text and organization of the signal layer. In particular, in the pictures described, the connotations are evidently double-conditioned. An active development of the connotations of the cross sign, Virgin, trumpeting Angel, Strelets’ poleaxes, animal snouts, and masks in the composition of *Boyaress Morozova* is conditioned in the aspect of semantic text and context, first of all, by religious and historical subject of the picture. On the other hand, these active connotations link major signals at the level of their representamens: large color configurations, structuring lines, directions of movement, focus points, visual centers, rhythmical structures, symmetries, and geometric constructions are organized (Somov 2005). The connotations of this kind can have different character in text actualization. In visual artworks, the text narrows the diapason of identifications, specifying the production of information. At the same time, characteristics are interrelated with object classes in different ways, i.e., a certain set of potential connotations is always present. This is why an image is often used to produce riddles and hints and to enhance imagination. Creating groups of characteristics corresponding to different classes of objects, we open a set of identifications and ways of their visual actualization. In semiotical models, this is described as semiosis in different dimensions (Lang 1993) or infinite semiosis (Eco).

The identification of visual objects is fixed in verbal-conceptual systems. People (known and unknown, of different ages, occupations, social and ethnic groups), cars of different makes and models, or clothes of different types are identified due to a stable fixation in grammatical and lexical structures and units of linguistic languages and texts. This helps to understand that the communicative structure of text of an artwork, its

hypertext, concept, and principal meanings (i.e., all verbal elements) are related with individual connotations via linguistic and textual systemities. If such interrelations among levels are absent, then indefinite and proper visual meanings are formed, which is described as a specific semiotic reality (Panofsky 1983 [1955]). An independent connotative layer of communication is formed, underlying the layer of verbal information. The elements — which cannot be clearly seen, named, and described verbally — form the world of hidden connotative formations of visual artworks included indirectly in the general tissue of a picture.

Connotations are formed along these lines: (1) signs (designates) — signs (designates) and (2) elements of sign (designates) — whole signs (designates). Semiotic scientists distinguish ‘horizontal’ and ‘vertical’ lines: *metaphors* and *metonymies*, respectively (Eco 1976; Chandler 1994). Both of them can exercise general functions of a text and functions inside a text. *Connotations — metaphors exercising general functions* appear in visual artworks as signs of other objects built in a picture (movement directions likened to lift, descent, or flight; icons of natural objects, people, animals, or tools), relating the text of a picture with external realities. *Connotations — metaphors exercising functions inside a text* of visual artwork usually promote the formation of unified systemities of denotations and connotations interrelated with basic signals. In *Boyaress Morozova*, typical systemities of this kind are: Morozova’s head repeated in the silhouettes of human beings, sledges, and road; the contour of Virgin at the icon repeated in the configuration of the crowd; Streletses’ poleaxes repeated in landscape lines; the two-finger sign of a lifted hand of Boyaress developed in the image of walking people. These and other systemities simultaneously organize active signals (large configurations, form-generating lines, and color accents) and express significant meanings of the picture: the image of persecuted heroine, Our Lady’s Protection, and the basic historical subject of the picture — schism. As denotations form metonymies, their metaphors inside the text strengthen the construction of these metonymies. Equities of characteristics and elements of representaments form semantic authentications and thus, activate the meaning of one characteristic (element) in the text. In addition, equities of characteristics carry out organizing functions proper by creating a structural organization of signal layer: color configurations, their contours, active lines, centers, and points differentiated by visual perception. If designates of connotations are part of more general and abstract designates, these are *connotations-metonymies*. In particular, they include images reflecting a certain general idea. In *Boyaress Morozova*, the trumpeting Angel hidden in the landscape denotes the Fifth Angel of Apocalypses pointing to the approaching of Doomsday. In *Virgin of Petrograd*, the

face with bared teeth occupying approximately one-half of the picture expresses an awful reality of the city, which, in its turn, symbolizes the revolution (Somov 2005). The formation of multilevel metonymies of this kind based on connotations makes large symbolization possible in visual artworks. This corresponds to the idea of formation of global symbolizations in art and spiritual life, which, according to E. T. Cassirer, is specific to human beings.

All this helps to understand why the search for connotations, means, and ways of their creation often occupies the central place in artistic explorations. The best illustration of this is the study of the works of the outstanding Russian painter M. A. Vrubel (1856–1910) revealing the connotations of visual artworks in many aspects.

2. Sources of connotative systems of Vrubel's language

The creative work of Vrubel united different and supposedly contradicting predilections: painting from nature, church frescos, book illustrations, decorative panels, theater stills, architecture, sculpture, and design. Thematic sources of his works were equally diverse: the motives of the Antics, European Middle Ages, ancient Slavic epics and tales, and poetry by A. S. Pushkin and M. Yu. Lermontov. The search for artistic tools was correspondingly wide; the artist himself called this the 'search for language'¹ (Vrubel 1937). It was based on an integrated vision of the world. 'Naive individual vision, all the strength and source of painter's delight'; 'the wholeness of human is manifested in this completeness of vision' (Vrubel 1937: 179). The assimilation of forms of the environment was based on this individual vision of nature; this determined the fundament of sign systems of M. Vrubel. In his letters, the painter wrote much about the necessity of following, exploring, and admiring nature. According to Vrubel, form is the most important thing that nature gives art; he wrote that the summits of art were achieved by those who 'could use this form for majestic compositions breathing with motion ...' (Vrubel 1937: 177). From the viewpoint of semiotics, the forms acquired by the artist from studying nature have a connotative metaphoric character. This vision is very apparent in artist's letters. In the fragment of a letter dated 1883 written at Peterhoff (near St. Petersburg) and addressed to painter's parents, Vrubel wrote:

In the evenings, instead of listening music, I stare at a quiet picturesque fishermen's life. One of their old men caught my fancy: his face is dark like an old copper five-kopec coin, with weather-stained yellowish hair and felted beard; a

smoked and pitched black-and-white jersey coats his senile body with prominent shoulder-blades; inside and from above, his boat has the color resembling weathered bone, while from the keel side, it is wet and velvety green, like the back of a marine monster, with patches made of a fresh wood silkily glittering at the sun and resembling straw surfaces. (Vrubel 1937: 178)

From the forms of nature, the painter selected those containing connotations. V. A. Serov, who shared the house with Vrubel when the latter was creating his *Demon* (1885) described the way Vrubel used a photo of mountains: 'An inverted photo represented an extremely complex ornament resembling an extinct crater or Moon landscape. This is why the photo was used to create the background of the picture' (Yaremich 1911: 69–70). In the photos, the forms were generalized and obtained a connotative character. This is why the painter took the motives of illuminated land, plants, and cloth folds from the photo; this was the refraction of real object through a prism (Vrubel 1937: 183). In its turn, this 'prism' was interpreted by the painter as the plastic manifested in form (Vrubel 1937: 175) and as 'music appearing as it is in ornaments and architecture' (Vrubel 1937: 185; Yaremich 1911: 130). The music of images was formed in the interrelations of connotations with the world of symmetries and rhythms, geometry and topological features. Therefore, the forms of nature, which were especially significant for the painter, simultaneously were connotative and organized the structure of the layer of image signals.

Artistic traditions caused an independent influence on the formation of Vrubel's language. He followed certain prototypes already making his wall paintings at St. Cyril church (1884). The icons for this church were painted in Venice where Vrubel studied Byzantine mosaics and works of great painters of the past. The painter modestly pointed to the dependence of his works on the mosaics of St. Mark Cathedral and works by Carpaccio, Giovanni Bellini, and Cima da Coneliano (Yaremich 1911: 62). The following of Byzantine and Venetian traditions determined the semiotic systems of Vrubel to a large extent. Byzantine artists tended to find 'pure' forms, which corresponded to Byzantine theology, with its ideas of direct influence of Prototype, divine form, and divine energy on a person. The Venetians also followed this search, as 'Byzantine art was a kind of prism of visual art for them' (Yaremich 1911: 188). They diverged even further from direct denotations by transforming images into hardly perceptible connotations. This tendency became the most apparent in the works by the artists who were the most respected by Vrubel: G. Bellini and J. Tintoretto (Vrubel 1937: 181). Having a similar vision of the world, the painter developed some of their principles and techniques. Vrubel's studies of Tintoretto became the fundament of interpretation of

general approach to composition. Art critics described the following features of this approach:

In the pictures by Tintoretto, everything follows the will of mysterious higher forces: they carry a spectator along, making him their blind instrument, fill the pictures with confusion and anxiety. People painted by Tintoretto are always in motion, but it is not the motion of active and creative persons; these involuntary jests express the outburst of soul and agitation gripping people . . . There is always something seeming and ghostly in the painter's world, his people are not sanguineous beings but resemble mysterious shadows seen in a dream. (Alpatov 1949: 130–131)

The main connotations forming these forces and movements are likening crowds of people and their motions to natural elements. The 'paradise' by Tintoretto, so much admired by Goethe, resembled plants; it was a kind of landscape, place, and transfigured nature, and not only the ensemble of holy persons (Benua 1913: 362). In this aspect, the painting anticipated the visions of science fiction writers of the twentieth century. This high connotativity of Tintoretto's pictures determined his approach to sketch and color. 'With his search of general impressions, an accurate work with details was certainly impossible . . . For to the same reason, the painting by Titian webbed of pure and sonorous colors was unavailable for him. A kind of pollution and even blackness is noticeable in his colors.' (Alpatov 1949: 131–132). Vrubel accepted these features of the art language of Tintoretto. He formed basic connotations as those subordinated to higher forces. The painter himself said that he tended to express higher principles and majesty (Yaremich 1911: 92). In many works, he subordinated the composition to the motion and energy of natural elements, undulating water, gusts of wind, the movements of clouds, the might of mountains, the hardness of stones, the forces of snow and ice, the vital energy of plants, the motion of submarine monsters, bird flight, etc. In this way, Vrubel created natural energetic connotations: silhouettes moving in flight and rush, wavy movements, creeping and trembling shadows, pulsing waves similar to those implemented in the paintings by Tintoretto.

The works by G. Bellini also markedly influenced Vrubel's language. Bellini possessed a technique that allowed him to introduce disturbing states and a mystic feeling of the presence of invisible creatures into an image, to subordinate a picture to a motion, rush, and confusion, or pacification and rest, and to fill it with ghosts and spirits. These means, specific for works by Bellini, can be characterized, first of all, as the dissonance between major color configurations and contours and denotations, which is manifested as the smear and stratification of represented objects.

Bellini introduced active elements, which changed sharply the structure of signals by powerful contrasts of light-and-shadow and color (earth breaks, active lines of plants, shadows, forms of folds, etc.). These stratifications of color connotations and lines into active and mutually contrast geometrical figures on a plane and their separation from denotative functions led to the evolution of such integrities into independent connotative structures and formation of multiple connotations. Vrubel often used these features of visual art language in his works. Appealing to G. Bellini and his predecessors, Byzantine artists, Vrubel borrowed one of main principles of this language, which is the destruction of connotations and strengthening of the plane by this destruction. In particular, Vrubel noted that cloth folds in Byzantine mosaics and wall paintings, created boldly and monumentally, strengthen the plane (Yaremich 1911: 52). Following the traditions of Byzantine artists and search of G. Bellini, the painter actively destroyed basic denotations of images promoting a direct effect of color, masses, and forms. This was achieved not only via intricate cloth folds, like in Byzantine art, but via pronounced fractures, sharp turns, cuts, and twinkling on the surface of depicted objects. In general, in most of his pictures, Vrubel followed the path of stratification of denotative icons and signals, creating heterogeneities of signals filled with connotations and organized into complex ornamental compositions. This was enhanced by mosaic fragmentation of images into separate configurations of various colors, directions, dimensions, and forms. The painter developed this approach painting in watercolors when he followed the technique of Fortuni (Yaremich 1911: 29; Vrubel 1937: 527). By destroying denotations and creating visual heterogeneities, he had the possibility to form indefinite, intertwining, and pulsing connotations. Indefinite and complexly interlacing geometric forms and color configurations turned into the material of hidden images: ghosts, monsters, animals, plants, mermaids, etc. On this basis, a specific semiotic systemity was formed in the creative work of Vrubel. Those who study his works call it 'decorative style'; it reached maximum 'richness and awkwardness' in 1890s (Yaremich 1911: 136; Sarab'yanov 1981). These peculiarities of Vrubel's language unite his works with semiotic systems of Art Nouveau as a whole and its different artists (A. van de Velde, J. Olbrich, M. Klinger, F. von Stuck, etc.). The semiotic systemity worked out by the painter allowed him, if necessary, to deviate from the denotation of real and mystic objects to abstract art, to fill concrete images with multilateral semantics, and, primarily, to express higher spiritual forces, as the painter himself tended to do (Yaremich 1911; Sarab'yanov 1981). The mobility and free stratification of representamens into the layer of signals and decorative ornament, the creation of interrelated connotations forming indefinite

but united semantic fields of images — all this made it possible to organize each layer of work as a relatively independent one and to form a developed basis of multiple unverbalizable meanings.

3. Typical semiotic systems and connotative formations of artworks

Studies of the painter's works devoted to different themes make it possible to reveal the origin and development of different semiotic systems and predominating connotations. Basic differences in the art themes of Vrubel determined the differences in approaches, directions of stylization, and connotation types.

A significant place in Vrubel's creative work belongs to the poetry by Yu. M. Lermontov, most of all, his poem *The Demon*. It was illustrated in 1890–1891. The illustrations were made with the help of black watercolor on large paper sheets (figures 1–7).

The spiritual affinity of the illustrations to Lermontov's poetry is determined, to a large extent, by the structure of images proper. The specificity of connotations in the structure of illustrations is represented by their nonverbal origin. The poetry by Lermontov is based on motions, sounds, mountain echo, resonant sounds of falling stones, roar of mountain streams, visions of clouds, giant towers, clustering mountains, forests, and valleys, which expose themselves in the Demon's flight. These meanings rely upon the feeling of movement (fall, run, and flight), sonic substance of the environment, and tactile sensation of its objects. They are these fundamental codes and signs, which serve as the basis of the visual connotations of Vrubel's illustrations to the poem by Lermontov. Visual characteristics represent the signs of movements, blows, rustles, musical rhythms, and lovemaking. In connection with this, structural formations represent the connotations of the most important episodes. Signal formations organize the plane of images, promoting their identification and memorization. This is why the illustrations create pronounced contrasts of major structural formations of signals (see figures 8–14).

The dance of Tamara (figures 1 and 8) represents the interrelations between a visible world of human life and the Demon, invisible to human beings. People at the foot of the image are covered with the spirit's wings. This symbolizes demonic forces hanging over the rejoicing of life. This general connotation is reinforced by the contrast of organization of top and bottom of the picture. The circular rhythmic dance is expressed with the help of rhythmic blows: directions of musical instruments and turnings of musicians' heads. Above, the Demon's wings form a vertical structure. They hang over the joyous dance like feathers of a vulture waiting

Figure 1. *Mikhail Vrubel, 'Tamara's Dance.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).*

Figure 2. Mikhail Vrubel, 'Riders.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

Figure 3. Mikhail Vrubel, 'A horse rushes faster than a fallow-deer ...' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

Figure 4. Mikhail Vrubel, 'Tamara and the Demon.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

Figure 5. *Mikhail Vrubel, 'The Demon and Cloisters.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).*

Figure 6. Mikhail Vrubel, 'Tamara in the Coffin.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

Figure 7. Mikhail Vrubel, 'The Demon.' Illustration to Lermontov's poem 'The Demon' (1890, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

Figure 8. 'Tamara's Dance.' Connotation — the rejoicing of life is covered with huge wings of the Demon.

Figure 9. 'Riders.' Connotation — the sharp cuts of jagged lines form a jagged wound of the impending slaughter.

Figure 10. 'A horse rushes faster than a fallow-deer ...' Connotation — rhythms of horse's hooves and impetuous glimpses of surrounding stones.

Figure 11. *'Tamara and The Demon.'* Connotation — the interwoven flow of soft caressing lines symbolizing sweet dreams.

Figure 12. *'The Demon and Cloisters.'* Connotation — sharp wedges and acute angles form intensity, express powerlessness, and the torments of separation.

Figure 13. 'Tamara in the Coffin.' Connotation — the contours of the head and face designate the self-enclosed world of death and eternal rest.

Figure 14. 'The Demon.' Connotation — the large broken contours of mountains and the head of the Demon form the stark world of loneliness in stone and ice.

for his prey. Opposing riders (figure 2) are depicted by sharp and exaggeratedly ragged contours. Lines and areas of different tones predominate in the picture, which prevents the perception of depicted Caucasian *dzhigits* and puts a spectator out from a clear interpretation of their images. This is explained by the subordination of major elements of the illustration to a general connotation: basic contours and lines form here something resembling a large avulsed wound pointing to a forthcoming massacre (figures 2 and 9). The illustration titled 'The horse would outrun a fallow-deer ...' makes an impression of the rush of a horse with a dying rider (figures 3 and 10). The rider and rushing horse form a merged mass. Dashed lines denote hoof clatter; flowing together in strong straight lines, these lines, with their increasing rhythms, correspond to the vision of dashing landscape. The main effect of the picture is due not to a true representation of careering horse and rider, but, first of all, to the revealing of the basic features of rush and subordination of all major elements to this determinant connotation. The Demon rambling near a convent (figures 4 and 11) is the illustration designed to wake spectator's compassion. The image is organized by powerful geometric structures. An almost falling silhouette of the Demon assigns a kind of uncertainty and aimlessness to his wandering around the convent. The fluttering of a dark silhouette with hard trapeziform and triangle contours expresses a craving for a sweetheart. In this case, intentional codes are crucial in the formation of connotation. However, the main meaning is skillfully reinforced by a concrete image: the grate protecting the entrance to the convent is as detailed as the face of the wistful Demon. This makes it a significant sign specifying the meanings of imprisonment and separation. Tamara and the Demon (figures 5 and 12) is the episode of Tamara's dream. Flowing lines are likened to charming sounds of the voice casting a spell over the heart and caressing movements; they express vague and sweet reminiscence of the dream. These lines form the fundament of dark and light configurations and thereby construct the denotations of the picture. Tamara in a coffin (figures 6 and 13) is the illustration representing an easily memorable, symbolic, enclosed contour of a face. Together with vertical elements separating the right part of the image, this denotes an enclosed world of death. The Demon in the mountains (figures 7 and 14) symbolizes the general mood of the hero. The chopped contours of Demon's head and silhouette, likened to the delineation of mountains, are firm and cold. Firmness and cold, complemented with haze and uncertainty, express a cold, impassive world of a lonely suffering spirit. The critics pointed out that Vrubel deviated from the representation of the evil Demon created by Lermontov and assigned him the character of a not only lonely but suffering and sublime spirit (Suzdalev 1980; Dmitrieva 1984). However,

the main idea uniting the creative work of poet and painter is present. The poem *The Demon*, like all of Lermontov's poetry in general, was based on the central idea of philosophy of personalism: human spiritual solitude. Vrubel possessed a deep understanding of Lermontov's ideas; in the theme of the Demon, he developed the states and images corresponding to this idea by creating the pictures of icy, shining, and silent kingdom of Caucasus as global representation of solitude.

In 1886, working with decorative panels representing the episodes of *Faust*, the painter used typical motives and art tools of Gothicism. Gothic architectural motives of towers, gabled roofs, and lancet arches form a semantic field of Gothic cities. Plants, human silhouettes, and fragments of medieval architecture are represented by color configurations and broken, curved, and dashed contours resembling the motives and constructions of Gothic stained-glass windows. This interpretation came to Vrubel after his previous work with the sketches of stained-glass windows in 1895 (the Knight, Romeo and Juliet, etc.). In general, these panels carry a common semantic field of the Gothic cities where the depicted episodes and placed. The most important panel of this series is *The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles* (figure 15). Later on, the composition of panel was altered: an arch was cut out in its top (figure 16). Here, the figure represents a reproduction of the initial composition.

Major denotations (riders' silhouettes) are subordinated to a general semantic system. Faust looks forward, while Mephistopheles looks at the spectator, grinning ominously, because he alone can see us and the picture of eternity. However, the major meanings of the picture, like in other works by Vrubel, are formed by connotations rather than by denotations. Flying horses and riders form a living clot of forms changing with wind gusts (figure 17).

The waving of this flying mass is shown via the complexity of contours and color configurations. For the expression of an energetic and fluent flight, there was no need for a true depiction of horses' bodies and legs. Hence, their basic forms are subordinated to the representation of flight. Smooth contours of flying mass are opposed to the statics of sharp spires and towers of a sleeping city; as if a tousled cloud flies over a stark land. This opposition is of a metonymic character: gentle motion of the eternity is opposed to a set instant of terrestrial life. At the same time, major configurations and contours of the flying mass are organized in a definite way. First of all, the masses of painted objects are formed by crooked spiroid forms combined with straight directions, corresponding to a shining hilt of Faust's rapier (figure 18).

Hilt contours are developed in the image of flying horses and riders, their heads, cloth folds, and serpentine contours of burdocks (figures 19

Figure 15. Mikhail Vrubel, 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles' (1896, oil, panel, original picture [Yaremich 1911: 144]).

and 20). Turning Faust's rapier into a sign system and hiding his face in a shadow, Vrubel makes this sign important as a metonymy. The axis of the rapier is actively materialized by a brilliant spheroid end projecting from under the cloak. Contours of the most important elements of the image are similar to roses (figure 21).

The flowers form a paradigmatic range with another panel of this cycle where Faust and Margaret are painted near a huge rose bush. In *The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles*, the roses turn into burdocks, rising

Figure 16. Mikhail Vrubel, 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles' (1896, oil, altered panel, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

flames, and gusts of smoke, as if the ground burns under riders' feet (figure 22). These connotations have a sense similar to flashes of lightning expressed by broken lines intersecting in the visual center with Faust's bright star-shaped spur (figure 23). The lines of horses and riders and their cloths form contours of craniums with yawning empty eye-sockets hinting at the death and spiritual ruin in the immortality given by the

Figure 17. *'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.'* Connotation — the basic configurations are reminiscent of flowers and stones.

devil (figures 24 and 25). Dynamic lines of the fluttering horse manes and snouts and riders' cloths, together with the image at the bottom of the picture, form the silhouettes of lions (figures 26 and 27). Lions stepping gently to the earth surface symbolize invisible mastery of the world. In general, a system-structural formation of connotations is created, including the forms of denotations and major signals: color configurations, lines, and points. Due to the systemity of signals, the representamens of one type of connotations are simultaneously parts of representamens of

Figure 18. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — the basic masses forming a flying clot in the sky.

other ones. Clusters of flying forms turn into the contour of handle and flames; lines of flames turn into roses; roses turn into smoke, lion manes, and craniums. The connotations have no definite communicative structure, however, they are bound with a common context — text of a famous poem, its meanings, and concepts. In general, due to a complex connotativity, a symbolic ominous mood of the picture is formed.

The pictures illustrating Slavic epics and tales contain semiotic systems designed to fill the works with images and spirits of this imaginary world.

Figure 19. *'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.'* Connotation — the sword-hilt and its development in form-bearing lines.

The painter himself said that 'an intimate national tune that I aspire to catch on canvas and in ornament can be heard here' (Vrubel 1937: 185). The language of Slavic theme is developed at several levels of connotations. The works represent well-known mythological and fabulous characters, conventionalized images of real and fantastic environment; all this forms the denotations of this theme. However, the formation of connotations is the most important: characteristics of represented objects and images themselves form the world of icons, spirits, and feelings — specific

Figure 20. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — the outlines of a sword-hilt.

meanings corresponding to Slavic mentality. Basic forms of represented objects become fluent, coating, and seemingly caressing each other (sculptures of Snow-Maiden and Lel', images of naiads, mermaids, and princess Volkhova). While representing epic and fantastic heroes and episodes of heroic deeds, the forms are rounded too, but firm and martial. Typical examples of this direction are the sketches and final variant of the panel *Mikula Selyaninovich*, prepared for the exhibition in Nizhnii Novgorod and illustrating the meeting of two epic heroes: Mikula and Il'ya of

Figure 21. *'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.'* Connotation — the rose's flower.

Murom calling him to join a campaign against enemies. The comparison of initial and final versions demonstrates how the painter searched for interrelations among denotations, connotations, and organization of signals. In the first sketch, the painter reached a visual, signed, and proper connotative unity of the picture using various topological and geometric characteristics. The silhouettes of men and horses were subordinated to a quite mutual approach expressing the meeting of two heroes; they were organized by quite smooth contours and generally subordinated to the composition of the plane, which was formed as an extremely complex

Figure 22. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — puffs of smoke, rising in the sky, interconnected with the outlines of a rose.

multicolored ornament. Circular, rounded, curly, local, and finely dissected color configurations formed an ornamental plane, where an important function was carried out by contrasts of these configurations by a range of characteristics. The representation of contours of the moving horse, the peasant, and the rider corresponded to these color configurations. In the final version, Vrubel deviated from the ornamental character and developed primarily expressive connotations, subjecting forms to a forceful movement, blast, expression of vigor of horses and power of

Figure 23. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — broken lines and flashes forming lightning. At the center of their crossing is Faust's sparkling spur.

heroes. Pictorial elements gained their own fantastic connotations. Contours of horses' manes turned into snakes, snake movements turned into wings of flying crows resembling fantastic birds. The painter deviated from true historical facts when forming the signs and spirit of epic and fantastic world. His language is free form, a direct citation of historical and ethnographical details (costume, weapon, or architectural forms) but it generalizes typical elements of Slavic culture. This generalization is the most apparent in the projects of chimneys, stoves, and exhibition halls.

Figure 24. *'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.'* Connotation — the outline of a skull.

For example, the forms of chimneys do not repeat any of traditional Russian form, but represent the combinations of configurations, contours, and ancient Slavic ornamental motives (figures 28 and 29).

Vrubel's sign formations in architecture develop some general traditional structural characteristics: three and four component structures of main elements, encountering of embrasures, irregularity of contours, outlines of arches, and images of swans, fantastic birds, and snakes, typical for ancient Slavic motives. The painter interlaced traditional zoomorphic connotations with half-figurative motives of ancient heroes, mermaids,

Figure 25. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — the outline of skulls and orbits.

and wood-goblins. The combination of these connotations — indefinite fantastic creatures hiding in thickets — created a unified visual semantics of fairy tale. The connotations of this kind are found, in particular, in the picture *The Pan* (figure 30).

Vrubel placed the Greek god in a typical Russian forest landscape. Combining the images of myth and reality, he made the spirit of the picture simultaneously ominous, sad, and cheerful. In order to form the image and spirit, the painter used fine tools. According to Greek mythology,

Figure 26. *'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.'* Connotation — the outline of a lion.

Pan is known to be the patron of cattle and head of fauns. Therefore, it is naturally that image elements contain the snouts of inhabitants of forests and meadows with bowed and twisted horns, ears, and beards (figures 31–37). The roughness of hairy, horned, and long-eared creatures is likened to the roughness of stumps, tree stems, and tumors; branching animal horns are analogous to archly crooked birch branches, with their bushy foliage, and to the form of a horned moon. Involute Pan's horns represent a concrete implementation of these multiple features forming

Figure 27. 'The flight of Faust and Mephistopheles.' Connotation — the outline of a lion, similar to larger outlines (see figure 26).

simultaneously the fundament of connotations and organization of all elements of the picture. Placing a Greek god in a Russian landscape, the painter likens him with the ancient Slavic ghost — a wood-goblin rambling in forests and misleading people. Together with the dusky landscape, this interpretation turns the joyous Greek god into a lonely and ever-suffering forest creature. An illusive similarity of Pan with Slavic forest ghosts is enhanced by the general contour of his body. Its outlines and forms resemble the inhabitants of Slavic forests and

Figure 28. Mikhail Vrubel, 'Mikula Selyaninovitch and Vol'ga' (fireplace, 1900, majolika, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow). The configurations of a relief and colors form intertwined images.

whirlpools — wood-goblin and water-sprite (figure 38). The features forming representaments of connotations in this picture evolve to the implementations of visual images, which are the most convenient for identification (Rosenfeld 1969; Shekhter 1967). S-shaped, tapering, and spiral contours of trees denote horns. In combination with long locks of dark hair and hidden snouts, more concrete images of horned and long-eared creatures are formed. In this case, the specificity of connotations lies in independent and concrete character of icons. Once the connotation is created, it includes an entire form of a denotative character: Pan's beard forms something resembling the head of wood-goblin (figure 34); the skin he is dressed in forms living creatures in the bottom of the picture (figures 33, 34, and 36); the contours of Pan's body and birch to the right encounter the head of cow (figures 31 and 37), etc. The interlacing and multiple repeating of ranges of characteristics of real and fantastic beings,

Figure 29. Mikhail Vrubel, 'Mikula Selyaninovitch and Vol'ga' (fireplace, 1900, majolika, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow). The connotations of the relief and the color suggest hidden icons of wood spirits, knights, and water nymphs.

complemented with the darkness of late dusk, forms a common semantic field. It produces an uncanny spirit, at which the painter seemed to be aimed.

The connotations corresponding to the major subject also can be found in allegoric works by Vrubel. In the allegoric sculpture of *Spring* (figure 39), image-forming connotations complement sculptured head and body. Spring tides form smooth and shining fragments of form (figure 40). A spirit-like man's head can be guessed on the right side of the headdress. A strange dress of Spring seems to be filled with flowers. At the same time, the dress is materialized by forest and water creatures waking up for life: tritons, snakes, and other beasts sliding over the body and head of the beauty (figure 41). Two bow-legged figures at the bottom, on Spring's breast, resemble frogs and correspond to the silhouette of ancient Slavic symbol of patroness of procreation (Rybakov 1994: 478).

Figure 30. Mikhail Vrubel, 'The Pan' (1899, oil, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).

This sign has the character of metonymy. Mascots of procreation denoting fertility are the most important signs of ancient Slavic semiotic systems (Rybakov 1994: 483). A concrete character of the beauty's face is dissolved in the vagueness of connotative plastic material. Indefinite silhouettes of living beings moving in water flows, head of a spirit, and forms of flowers make an impression of awakening of life; together with the tempting smile of the beauty, they form a united image of coming Spring.

In the pictures painted from nature, Vrubel also created developed connotations. A well-known portrait, *Fortune-teller* (figure 42), represents

Figure 31. 'The Pan.' Connotation — the contours of big-eared beasts.

a kind of a poem of card-reading and magic. Her strange look is directed at something mysterious far behind a spectator. This look is a sign inclusion in the art text of the work.

The ornament of carpet, interrelated with image proportions and fallen cards, forms the major connotations. Rectangular cells of carpet ornament corresponding to the rectangular cards denote the matrix of future events marked by the cards (figures 43 and 44). The face of the fortune-teller, dropped cards, the hand with the main card, another free hand, and golden bracelet form an integer systemity. The rectangular cards and matrix cells are related to a proportional system of the image as a whole

Figure 32. *'The Pan.'* Connotation — the contours of horned animals.

(figures 43 and 44). This strictly geometric grid is opposed to the scattered cards at the bottom, which represent the discourse of stochastic events. Card scattering is formed by the structure of the multiplication sign. The multiplication signs also form general contours of fortune-teller (figure 45), while their depiction in the rectangles of carpet cells resemble the signs of events of Chinese *Book of Changes*. In general, a common meaning of guessing future events is formed. This meaning is developed in the connotation of card symbols. The ace of spades predominates among scattered cards; it is developed as a connotative formation of the

Figure 33. *'The Pan.'* Connotation — animals' muzzles in color configurations.

whole picture (figure 46). In addition, its contours are read in active configurations as a heart symbolizing love sortilege (figure 47). The hidden faces of people searching for divination are built in a carpet patience denoting the probabilistic character of future events. Major lines of the picture form a resemblance of long beards of Eastern sages (figure 48). Circles encountered by dark belts, corresponding to the ring of dark hear of fortune-teller, form the connotations of eyes and, together with the contours of heads and faces, create the images of soothsayers and magi (figure 49). The most noticeable head hidden in carpet ornaments in the

Figure 34. *'The Pan.'* Connotation — muzzles and horns in the basic color configurations.

upper right corner (figures 49 and 50) resembles the wise, crowned biblical king, master of spirits. The silhouette and cloth of the fortune-teller hide the head of a Muslim warrior covered with a kerchief and turban, with an ardent eye and darkly grinning mouth (figures 49–51). Other faces of sorcerers and soothsayers are guessed in the carpet ornament. This connotation is spread over the whole order of the picture, sustained by the systemity of form-making lines and denotations (figure 52). The lines of the beard and the contour of the head of the master of spirits generate visually organizing directions and forms. In general, the conno-

Figure 35. 'The Pan.' Connotation — muzzles of cows and other beasts in the basic color configurations.

tations of the portrait have the character of metonymies, contributing to its generalized symbolic interpretation, and form basic system-structural formations of signals. The heart hinting to love sortilege and the card signs form the fundament of depiction of fortune-teller's head, face, and body: the card, with its proportions and signs, forms structural elements of the picture; the image of bearded soothsayers assigns a special character to form-making lines and color configurations of the picture. The characteristics forming major connotations of *Fortune-teller* are based

Figure 36. *'The Pan.'* Connotation — muzzles of cows in the basic lines.

on oppositions and produce active contrast groups of signals: rectangles, multiplication signs, encountered circles, and diagonal and vertical contours. In general, a united systemic structure of signals, correlated with connotations, is formed.

Figure 37. 'The Pan.' Connotation — muzzles of cows and other beasts in the basic lines.

Connotative formations were developed in different variations of *Demon*. Already the first sketches illustrating the poem by Lermontov contain noticeable hidden images of spirits and beasts. For example, in the picture dated 1898 (figure 53), a dispersed head of horse or dragon turned

Figure 38. *'The Pan.'* Connotation — the hidden image of a water-sprite's head or wood-goblin in the chiaroscuro and in the picture of Pan's figure.

to the right is distinguished. It assigns force and dynamic to the Demon's head. Later pictures on this theme also demonstrate the development of connotations of this kind. The background of the figure of the prostrated Demon painted in 1902 (figure 54) is painted as an indefinite graphic

Figure 39. *Mikhail Vrubel, 'Spring' (sculpture, majolica, 1899–1890, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).*

Figure 40. *'Spring.' Connotation — the shiny parts of the sculpture forming vernal waters.*

Figure 41. 'Spring.' Connotation — the large parts of the sculpture's relief form icons of living water creatures. The relief of a head-dress forms the image of a spirit.

matter: mountains, stones, and wings of a fallen angel represented as the plumage of Firebird. This uncertainty creates a good basis for the formation of connotative structures. The painter made the picture of background elements — Firebird's wings — to resemble a richly embroidered flying carpet on which the thoughtful Demon lies. The ornament of this carpet hides the bodies and snouts of living creatures (figures 55–57). The faces of mountain spirits can be guessed in the contours of the pictures (figure 58). These strange polyvariant images set into the picture create a mystic mood accompanying the theme, as the mysticism presupposes the existence of the world of other creatures, which is parallel to our world.

The last outstanding picture of the painter, *Vision of Prophet Ezekiel* (1905) corresponds completely to this idea. The images of prophets, angels, and spirits were so apparent that they were available to contemporary spectators (Yaremich 1911: 172). Very likely, the complete demonstration of connotations in the last picture is due to the fact that it was painted when the artist was already insane (Yaremich 1911: 173–174).

Figure 42. *Mikhail Vrubel, 'Fortune-Teller' (1895, oil, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).*

Figure 43. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — the fortune-telling card and proportions of basic elements.

Figure 44. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — the fortune-telling card and proportions of basic icons.

Figure 45. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — the oblique crosses: the signs of an insight into events form a structural basis for the construction of the image.

Figure 46. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — the ace of spades heading fortune-telling cards, forms a sign system of the composition as a whole.

Figure 47. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — signs of hearts hint at amorous fortune-tellings. The central small heart (upside down) is the Fortune-Teller's face.

Figure 48. 'Fortune-Teller.' Signals and connotations — the basic lines of the image serve as bases for the development of connotations of ancient, long-bearded wise men, magi, and soothsayers.

Figure 49. 'Fortune-Teller.' Comnotation — magi and soothsayers, basic contours.

Figure 50. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — magi and soothsayers in color configurations.

Figure 51. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — hidden faces reminiscent of spirits.

Figure 52. 'Fortune-Teller.' Connotation — hidden faces in the basic lines.

Figure 53. *Mikhail Vruble, 'Demon' (1898, black watercolor, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow). Connotation — the head of a dragon or a horse developed to the right in the Demon's hair.*

Figure 54. *Mikhail Vruble, 'Demon prostrated' (1902, oil, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow).*

Figure 55. *'Demon prostrated.'* Connotation — hidden figures of living creatures on coloured configures.

Figure 56. *'Demon prostrated.'* Connotation — hidden figures of animals in the colored configurations.

Figure 57. *'Demon prostrated.'* Connotation — hidden figures of animals and spirits in the colored configurations.

Figure 58. 'Demon prostrated.' Connotation — spirits in a drawing of the picture's elements.

Note

1. Quotations from Vrubel (1937), Yaremich (1911), and Alpatov (1949) have been translated from Russian by the author.

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